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Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF AUTOMATIC MALARIA DISEASE DETECTION USING THE SYSMEX XN 30 ANALYZER IN A THERAPEUTIC SETTING

¹Sidratul Muntaha, ²Aqsa Khaild, ³Dr Sania Hussain

¹Fatima Jinnah Medical University, ²Fatima Jinnah Medical University, ³Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore.

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Abstract:

Aim: Early and effective diagnosis of Malaria is a vital part of the disease control campaign, and a few suggestive instruments are available. Tiny blood fringe test empowers the precise representation of parasites in infected red platelets and is the highest performing scientific analytic. However, it is emotional and needs a higher degree of capacity.

Methods: Various aberrant position methods are being used, but are not optimal because proxy disease markers are approximate. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. This investigation reveals the key therapeutic execution appraisal of the mechanized Sysmex XN-30 analyzer, which uses fluorescence flow cytometry to quickly classify and measure red parasite-trained platelets.

Results: Residual EDTA blood tests from alleged Malaria cases identified for routine conclusion have broken down on the XN-30. Parasitaemia was accounted for as a rate, just as an absolute quantity of tainted red platelets, and dispersed grams provided a visual representation of the parasitized red platelet groups. The findings detailed in the XN-30, related to the microscopy and the analyzer, showed 100% affectability and explicitness. Estimates were reproducible, and the handling of room temperature samples did not affect limits. Several animal types of Plasmodium have been described, including Plasmodium falciparum, Plasmodium vivax and Plasmodium ovale. The XN-30 likewise distinguished infectious gametocytes as a separate bunch of scatter grams. Irregular red platelet reports (low hemoglobin, elevated reticulocyte checks), haemoglobinopathies and thrombocytopenia did not interact with the detection of parasites. By the same token, the XN-30 provided a simultaneous full blood mean for each case.

Conclusion: The epic invention of the System XN-30 provides a solid, quick, mechanized and reliable stage for the diagnosis of Malaria in a clinical environment. The target number of red platelets infected with Plasmodium species makes it ideal for worldwide use and helps the monitoring of the parasite load at any point before therapy is begun, resulting in an early predictor of drug resistance. The robotic age of full blood ensures that each example gives an opportunity to recognize unsuspected events. Asymptomatic transporters will also be distinguished, which can be useful in concentrating on blood bonds, which will enable these individuals to avoid the spread of infection.

Keywords: Automatic Malaria Disease Detection, System Xn-30 Analyzer.

Corresponding author:

Sidratul Muntaha,

Fatima Jinnah Medical University.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Intestinal diseases remain perhaps the leading parasitic infection in the world, with more than 3.2 billion people in 91 nations at risk of infection [1]. The effect of disease on clinical and public welfare is a topographical factor, depending on the force of transmission and the species of parasites involved. The World Health Organization's 2018 report on Malaria shows that in 2017, there were approximately 218 million cases worldwide, with an expected loss of 435,000 lives. 93% of the cases of transmission of the disease occurred in sub-Saharan Africa, mainly among children and pregnant women [2]. The report also shows that after a period of unusual success in the global fight against jungle fever, the number of cases has risen and progress has slowed. Worryingly, few countries with a disproportionate burden of the disease have experienced a detailed rise in the number of Malaria cases. Remarkably, the ten African countries most affected by the disease recorded 4.6 million more cases in 2017 compared to the previous year [3]. In this regard, the effort is expected to reverse this trend, and every case of intestinal disease prevented and denied contributes to the global campaign for elimination. To adequately combat the burden of intestinal diseases, it is important to detect them quickly and accurately [4]. Correct analysis will not only allow reliable recognition of Malaria from different causes of intense febrile illness, but will also allow explicit treatment to be started in this way, which will also prevent complexities and reduce mortality. It is unfortunate that the clinical results are not explicit enough and not precise enough, even with a history of movement, because the clinical manifestations and indications of Malaria are regularly vague and may reflect other

tropical diseases. As WHO states, the discovery of clinically dependent bowel disease often encourages overtreatment and unreasonable use of drugs against malaria specialists [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Using fluorescence flow cytometry, the XN-30 also recognizes red and white blood cells contaminated with intestinal disease (RBC-IM). It contains a blue semiconductor laser with a 409 nm stem, which differentiates it from the usual Sysmex hematology analyzers, which have a red semiconductor laser with a 633 nm stem. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. In contrast to red light, the frequency of blue light is more limited, which makes it possible to discover smaller particles. During the discovery period of the intestinal disease, a recently developed reagent permeabilizes the cell film of the red blood cells halfway, allowing the entry of a reagent with fluorescent properties, which stains the nucleic acids of the parasites. At the time an example is examined, the number of red blood cells is estimated using a direct current (DC) discovery technique and the control of red blood cells contaminated with Malaria is estimated by fluorescence cytometry. The level of contamination of red blood cells with intestinal disease is determined from the proportion of extraordinary red blood cell controls (MI-RBC# and RBC) obtained by the two strategies. Like the usual Sysmex analyzers, the XN-30 also uses the sheath flow DC recognition strategy to decide on other records, including hematocrit in addition, platelet verification, and a sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) strategy to estimate hemoglobin.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

RESULTS:

A total of 1035 examples prepared on the model analyzer yielded substantial results worthy of further study. There were 264 positive examples of intestinal disease (*P. falciparum*: n = 158; *P. vivax*: n = 104), 261 negative tests for Malaria in patients with suspected intense febrile illness, 268 negative obstructive tests for intestinal disease, 129 examples with standard BCF estimates; in addition, 100 others arbitrarily selected BCF tests from the normal research facility in India. Recognition of bowel disease by the XN-10 (M) analyzer was confirmed by an affectability of 98.8% (96% certainty over a period of 96.0 to 97.8%) and an explicitness of 99.8% (96% certainty over a period of 98.6 to 98.4%). In eleven smear-negative cases, the XN-10 (M) identified intestinal diseases, all of which were thus affirmed by PCR as true positive results. In addition, a "disengaged by platelet drop control" obstruction test appeared to give a false positive result

for XN-10 (M), but was confirmed in this way by the smear investigation as an unsuspected case of true jungle fever. All other obstructive tests, as well as all typical examples with interpretable results (see next section), were recognized as negative for malaria. There was no distinction in the execution of the recognition of intestinal diseases according to *Plasmodium* species. The analyzer effectively recognized the species as *P. falciparum* in 99% of cases (with 95% certainty over a period of 94.2-99.3%) and no *falciparum* in 95.9% of cases (with 96% certainty over a period of 89.5-97.8%). The greatest weakness is the high rate (15.9%) of uncertain results. In the event that the molecule included in the "M" channel exceeded the lower limit of quantification, but no indubitable cluster was observed in the region of intestinal disease onset, the analyzer then created a "strange MI-RBC scatter gram" and did not report the presence of jungle fever.

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

DISCUSSION:

Some gatherings have shown the ability of robotic analyzers to analyze Malaria in atypical light dissipation patterns due to the presence of haemozoin inside phagocytic leukocytes [6]. Nevertheless, these are devious strategies for recognizing the parasite and depend on the host's safe response to the microbe, hence Malaria analysis would require microscopic verification in all cases. In addition, haemozoin can continue to circulate on monocytes [7]. Subsequently, the computerized localization of haemozoin undergoes a constraint similar to that of RDTs, where positive results can be obtained after the patient has been treated with antimalarial specialists and the parasites have been eliminated [8]. The finding of intraerythrocytic haemozoin has also been considered, but it is of limited value in diagnosing *P. falciparum* intestinal disease [9]. This report is the main description of the reasonable and clinical utility of computerized and direct recognition of intestinal disease parasites in red blood cells of infected patients using the Sysmex XN-30 analyzer. It showed brilliant affectability and was explicit for *P. falciparum* parasites, which it quantified accurately and reproducibly. The consequences of XN-30 parasitaemia are hence related to the current highest clinical quality level in the field of intestinal diseases, making it as efficient as a reference microscope for the determination of intestinal diseases in the clinical setting [10].

CONCLUSION:

The ideal discovery of a bowel disease is a life-saving one, and while most experts in medical services are ready to perceive the disease, the clinical introduction is regularly vague and determination may be overlooked at first. The XN-30 analyzer is an ideal methodology for the accurate recognition and robotic counting of parasitaemia in intestinal diseases. It quickly identifies the actual parasite with no result, e.g. antigens, phagocytic parasites or haemozoin, which makes the identification of the intestinal disease thought to RTD and other aberrant robotic strategies more reasonable. Simultaneous estimation of hematological limits is a remarkable component that gives significant information to the clinical relationship. While it does not quickly supplant microscopy for the assertion of the clinical disease of jungle fever, the XN-30 should be considered as a complementary symptomatic instrument, as it can encourage the recognition of unsuspected cases. In general, this innovative advance may potentially fundamentally affect the methodologies indicative of jungle fever, useful observation as well, viability,

hostility to the disclosure of antimalarial drugs and clinical preliminaries.

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